

FLEXIBLE CONNECTION OF DISTRIBUTED ENERGY RESOURCES TO THE GRID

Hatice AYDIN

Necmettin Erbakan University, Faculty of Engineering, Department of Electrical-Electronics Engineering, Konya -Türkiye
ORCID: 0000-0002-2729-9503

Muciz ÖZCAN

Prof. Dr, Necmettin Erbakan University, Faculty of Engineering, Department of Electrical-Electronics Engineering, Konya -Türkiye
ORCID: 0000-0001-5277-6650

ABSTRACT

In many electricity distribution systems around the world, the penetration of Distributed Energy Resources at distribution levels is increasing due to the negative impact of traditional fossil fuel energy sources on the climate. This penetration is causing the traditional electricity distribution system to change rapidly. With this change, the way new smart technologies interact with the energy system is also changing. However, while a higher percentage of generation from traditional Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) is promising in terms of decarbonization, it will create problems for distribution system operators and asset owners (producers and consumers) in the long run. In this paper, we propose a new connection type, flexible connection concept, for electricity distribution grids where the number of distributed energy resources and power electronic devices is increasing. The flexible connection method aims to increase the hosting capacity of distributed generation resources, improve the power quality parameters of the grid, ensure energy supply-demand balance, ensure system reliability, and prevent negative market pricing and instability. Firstly, the definitions of the concept of flexibility in the electricity distribution system, flexible connection in the literature, why this concept is needed, and flexible generation, storage and consumption resources, which are flexible energy resource types, are examined. In the next section, the increasing need for flexible resources in electricity distribution systems, different flexibility mechanisms, flexible connection applications in the world are researched and sample applications are included. In addition, flexible connection and flexible curtailment methods, which are widely preferred and currently being implemented in the UK, are examined. In the last section, the benefits of integrating distributed energy resources into the system with flexible connection and the issues that need to be improved in practice are analysed. As a result of the study, it is concluded that flexibility will provide a significant increase in the integration of distributed generation resources, provide alternative connection options for generation plants that want to connect, contribute positively to the sustainability of the system when integrated both on the electricity distribution system side and on the user (producer or consumer) side, increase system resilience especially at times of peak energy consumption, and reduce operating and investment costs. Energy storage facilities appear to be an important factor in resilience. However, there are many issues that need to be developed and researched, such as flexible assets, flexibility parameters, the effects on the transmission side and the energy market etc.

Keywords: Distributed energy resources, Electric power systems, Flexible connection, Flexible concept, Flexible resources, Hosting capacity.

Introduction

Energy production technique is an important issue in terms of greenhouse gas emissions (Ritchie H, 2022). The energy sector is the sector most responsible for greenhouse gas emissions with a share of some 75%. Energy-related CO₂ emissions are projected to increase from 33 GHG in 2015 to 35 GHG in 2050 under current and planned policies (Gielen et al., 2019), and the share of renewable energy sources needs to increase from 25% to 85% by 2050 to meet the targets of the Paris summit agreement (Essayeh & Morstyn, 2023).

While renewable energy has the potential to meet the entire primary energy demand, it is not without its challenges. Power system flexibility is one of these challenges.

The lack of flexibility of modern power grids can be demonstrated by various factors such as insufficient supply to meet demand, especially during peak hours, significant reductions in renewable energy, balance of area violations, instability, unfavorable market pricing and others (Hussain et al., 2023).

The integration of distributed energy Resources (DERs) equipped with smart energy technologies into the distribution network benefits society both sociologically and economically, while ensuring the stability and reliability of the electricity distribution network operators. As we continue to integrate increasing DERs technologies into the system, the existing EDS structure needs to be synchronized with this change due to the landscape created by these variable generation sources (Department of Energy, 2015).

Since the existence of EDSs, the structure has been dependent on centralized large generation sources. However, with new technologies and developments, this structure is shifting to a dynamic paradigm. In the last 20 years, many DERs such as photovoltaic systems (PV), variable wind generators, electric vehicles (EV), fuel cells, energy storage systems (ESS), demand response and load shifting resources have been integrated into the existing grid (Arboleya et al., 2022).

However, the current power grid is not designed to handle these unpredictable load flows, which can cause system congestion and high peaks, known as the "duck curve" in many countries (Calero et al., 2022). The negative effects of high DERs penetration have been observed where oversupply causes negative pricing more than 100 times a year (Reed, 2017). In such cases, the typical solution to curtail renewable energy production has been shown to lead to uneconomic and zero-carbon electricity losses (Hussain et al., 2023).

Additionally, these new loads and DERs are extremely important to help balance supply-demand between generation and consumption and provide EDS with a flexible operating tool. However, there are many flexibility methods that are applied without considering the criteria to ensure the operational integrity of the EDS (Arboleya et al., 2022).

Maximizing the hosting capacity (HC) of electrical distribution systems (EDS) for DERs is an integral part of efforts to increase the share of renewable energy sources (RES) in electricity grids (Toghranegar et al., 2022).

This study examines the status of technologies available on the grid that can be developed for applications that provide greater system flexibility, including flexible generation and customer-focused distributed resources (Department of Energy, 2015).

Electricity Distribution System Flexibility

Due to the significant penetration of RES, traditional operating methods have been recognized as insufficient to meet fluctuations in net load (Kaheh et al., 2019). Flexibility has therefore emerged as a critical consideration in the design of future power systems dominated by RES.

The International Energy Agency (IEA) defines energy flexibility as "the ability of a building to manage its demand and generation in response to local climatic conditions, user needs and grid requirements" (Hussain et al., 2023). System flexibility is also defined as the need for the electricity system to adjust generation (generation flexibility) or consumption (demand side flexibility) to maintain a secure system operation, taking into account grid stability constraints and intermittent renewable energy resources (Freire-Barceló et al., 2022). Flexibility can also be defined as "a power system that can manage variability and uncertainty in both generation and demand while maintaining a satisfactory level of reliability at a reasonable cost over different time horizons". From these definitions, we can generally say that resilience refers to the capacity of an EDS to reliably maintain supply during temporary and large imbalances (Hussain et al., 2023).

Flexible DERs connectivity is expected to provide a service that can respond quickly to demands on the grid, providing additional energy to the grid when it is most needed. We can basically categorize flexibility resources as DERs, energy storage, consumer-side dispatchable loads and virtual flexibility solutions (Alizadeh et al., 2016).

Flexible Resources

Flexible DERs can adjust the consumption or generation of electricity at a specific location on the grid for a given period of time.

These include;

- Flexible generation resources (Electric vehicles, loads that can be changed or shortened over time (SL/CL), Combined heat and power (CHP) units, systems setting power supplied by distributed generation (DG) that can be distributed such as PV, wind)
- Flexible storage resources (Energy storage systems, including battery energy storage (BES), V2G technology)
- Flexible consumption sources (Replaceable residential loads represent loads whose use can be scheduled on demand. For example, irons, washing machines and dishwashers, air conditioners, heaters and coolers, etc.). Figure 1 shows the providers of flexibility services (Freire-Barceló et al., 2022).

Figure 1. Flexible energy source types

In the literature, grid-connected flexible resource types are divided into three categories as mentioned above. Distributed generation, bidirectional DERs and electricity consumption.

Each option includes different flexibility models in the EDS and therefore each category requires separate processing. Energy demand-side flexibility provides downstream flexibility, while DERs provide upstream flexibility. ESSs provide bi-directional flexibility, offering a wider variety of implementations.

Although these three types of different energy systems proposal a range of grid flexibility, their potential is under-utilized (Pearson et al., 2022).

The graph in Figure 2 shows the ideal load profile and its upward and downward elasticities. In this way, we can see downward as a situation where consumption is more and generation is less, and upward as a situation where generation is more and consumption is less. Desired load profile for distribution system operator (DSO) is a situation with less fluctuation and uncertainty.

Figure 2. Flexibility concept from production and consumption

The basic service in power systems is to ensure the balance between generation and consumption by securing the frequency of the system (Pedro et al., 2023). For the desired load profile, a more secure system can be created by utilizing both generation flexibility and consumption flexibility.

Flexible Connection Applications

When integrating the increasing amount of DERs into the EDS, the traditional approach of fit and forget is adopted. In fact, this approach only allows DERs to be integrated into the EDS up to a certain level in order to maintain system operational security and integrity. However, this approach prevents the flexibility potential of DERs from being used efficiently. The fit-and-forget policy can also be interpreted as avoiding over-sizing the grid to cope with reverse energy flows and capacity increases in the EDS (Silva et al., 2021). For the integration of more DERs, this approach will not be environmentally and economically efficient. DSOs should therefore go beyond this policy by taking advantage of DERs flexibility and introducing new operating models and innovations (Pearson et al., 2022).

The increasing need for flexible resources in electricity systems has led to the need to explore different flexibility mechanisms. One of the mechanisms that is becoming increasingly common in the EU is connection agreements, also called flexible connection. EDSs allow network users to establish off-premise network access.

For example, in the Walloon region of Belgium, all new DERs over 250 kVA are required to make flexible connections. In Germany, a 3% curtailment rule applies to all DERs connections to EDS.

In the UK, Electricity North West DSO offers some flexible connection options for generation and consumption customers and is working on additional offers for system security (Nouicer et al., 2023).

The iPower project established a "trade room" for local flexibility trading at the EDS level in Germany (IPower, 2009).

The PeerEnergyCloud project focused on building a virtual market platform of a microgrid for electricity trading in Germany and established a cloud-based energy trading system for excess generation (Soto et al., 2021).

The ECO-Grid project created a prototype of a future smart energy system in Europe with the aim of leveraging market forces and smart power consumption management to involve individual consumers in balancing an energy system with abundant renewable energy. But ECO-Grid EU's plans also include the possibility of creating a "win-win" situation where small and large electricity customers can save money on their electricity bills while at the same time relieving the power system, reducing investments in grid reinforcements and new grids in the long term (Gantenbein et al., 2012).

The Piclo project aims to provide data visualization for consumers and to offer Italy's first local flexibility market with E-Distribuzione (Open Utility a Glimpse into the Future of Britain's Energy Economy, n.d.).

The Empower project aimed to develop a local market Paradigm in Europe that includes three financial market platforms for local energy sales, local flexibility and trading of other services, enabling EDS to profit from the embedded flexibility of the user side. This project aimed to greatly enhance the positive impacts of DERs and improve the resilience and effectiveness of supply-demand programs (Local Electricity Retail Markets for Prosumer Smart Grid POWER Services, 2020).

As a different solution, techno-economic studies have also been proposed for local community solutions to assess the reliability of Demand Side Management (DSM), sizing grid assets or studying the suitability of technological solutions, by adopting smart operation solutions that derive flexibility from EDS connected consumption and generation assets. In the integration of flexibly connected DERs for long-term energy system planning through the Long Range Energy Alternative Planning (LEAP) project, taking into account different DSM strategies, types and levels for India with high DERs penetration (including both EE and peak load shifting), demonstrating cost savings of up to 18% and reductions in both total installed capacity and CO₂ emissions of up to 10% and 23% respectively through the simultaneous implementation of both supply-side and demand-side flexibility (Couraud et al., 2023).

Flexible Connection Types

In practice, the DSO offers 5 different flexible connection types to the customer from the flexible connection types applied in the UK, Ireland by ENA (Energy network association), which has been adopted by other countries.

- 1) Scheduled buy/sell connections: These offer customers flexible connection to the grid, with energy purchases or sales limited to certain periods of the day, week, month or year. For example, on a day of peak PV generation, wind generation may be limited during the day.
- 2) 3rd Party flexible connections: Some customers may also consider joint capacity and demand management, both installed and managed by the customer.
- 3) Single Manufacturer Active Network Management (SGANM): Manages only one producer and up to two constraints instead of managing multiple constraints and multiple producers.
- 4) Limited Power Supply Connections: This type of flexible connection is also used in cases where the generation capacity is larger than the installed generation capacity injected into the EDS.
- 5) Limitation connections to energy import: These are used where the installed asset has a capacity to deliver energy from the EDS that is greater than the agreed energy that needs to be delivered.

Flexible Curtailment Methods

There are three different approaches to determining the curtailment of flexible connections to manage congestion in EDS, all three of which are deterministic and rule-based:

- a) In the Last In First Out (LIFO) method, any binding grid constraint is solved by interrupting generators in the reverse order of their connection applications. In this way, generators are insulated against larger outages caused by other generators connecting after them, as shown in Figure 3.a).

Under Last In First Out (LIFO), each generation asset is assigned a position in the priority stack according to its application date.

When a new DERs makes a flexible connection, a queue is assigned according to the date of its inclusion in the system. This customer is evaluated according to this sequence for the duration of the connection agreement. In case of a curtailment in the EDS, the DSO determines the customer to be curtailed starting from the last row according to this sequence number. This means that in case of any curtailment, the lowest ranked customer will always be affected. With LIFO, the customer at the top of the queue is the least affected customer in the event of an outage at the EDS.

- b) Pro-rata method, where the curtailment in the region of an affected flexible link is shared equally among all generators energizing during the congestion, as shown in Figure 3.b). Pro-rata curtailment solves constraints according to the proportional contribution of each generator.

Figure 3. a) First-in last-out (LIFO) b) Pro-Rata graphical representation of applications

c) Curtailment Index, customers with a flexible connection to the EDS is given an estimated curtailment index. This index is used to determine the maximum outage duration that the customer will be affected in a year (Georgiopoulos et al., 2020). The DSO uses this index to determine the curtailment sequence, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Curtailment index according to producers' participation

In consideration for a faster and cheaper connection, the customer is based on accepting a contractual requirement for remote, real-time switching of the usual power flows by the DSO through automation. The amount of modification or curtailment varies according to the connection agreement (ENA, 2021).

When flexibility is analyzed by connection agreements; when they compared demand side flexibility in distribution grid between voluntary and mandatory agreements, they concluded that voluntary agreements may have benefits in terms of prosperity gains and network investment savings, but mandatory load shedding should also be applied to save grid investment.

In both cases, they find that mandatory connection agreements lead to higher prosperity levels and significant grid investment savings than in the absence of explicit demand-side flexibility. While mandatory agreements are also more equitable among both generating consumers and passive consumers, there are concerns that they may face public backlash from consumers who do not like to be constrained (Nouicer et al., 2023).

Challenges and Limitations

As mentioned earlier, due to the remarkable proliferation of DERs, it has been recognized that traditional operating methods are insufficient to handle fluctuations in net load. Flexibility is therefore emerging as a critical consideration in the design of future EDS dominated by DERs. The main sources of flexibility in such systems include distributed generation facilities, flexible loads on the consumer side, virtual flexibility solutions and energy storage facilities (Alizadeh et al., 2016).

Technically, an EDS flexibility service can be defined as the adjustment of power from a specific location within the grid, at a specific time, for a specific period of time. A flexibility service is therefore a service characterized by five features. Direction, electrical composition in power, start time, duration, temporal characteristics defined by the location base (Freire-Barceló et al., 2022).

Traditionally, planning for the expansion and upgrading of the EDS contributes to the connection of more DERs. However, in order to develop techno-economically efficient plans, new tools are needed to better represent the current situation and new management mechanisms to integrate DERs are required (Alvarez et al., 2022).

Figure 5 shows the renewable energy contributions of NECPs member countries until 2030 according to the NECPs (National energy and climate plans) report. The NECPs association is committed to a policy of maintaining and strengthening world leadership in renewable energy. It sees this not only as a matter of system security and imperative climate change policy, but also as an industrial policy imperative to fully harness the growth potential of clean energy (European Commission, 2019). It is obvious that energy production from RESs will increase further in the coming decades. This increase will cause the problem of "overproduction" in the system. Therefore, the demands of DSO for the flexibility of the system will also increase.

Figure 5. National renewable energy contributions.

It is normally accepted that energy demand is inflexible and must always be supplied. However, with the appearance of flexible assets, demand-side flexibility is expected to come to the fore. Demand-side flexibility brings with it the potential to realize the flexibility to improve energy efficiency and further reduce costs. Flexibility at the distribution level is defined in the literature as the provision of flexibility from distributed assets i.e., solving system congestion, minimizing power loss or voltage deviation.

One of the reasons why they are currently unable to exploit their flexibility potential is the current structure of the power system. Currently, energy storage facilities with high flexibility potential for load shifting, fast demand response, etc. can be integrated into the system (Pearson et al., 2022).

ESS represents a crucial component in the future flexibility portfolio, especially in terms of cost relative to other flexibility assets. Flexibility in EDS with ESS provides three important benefits;

- 1) By improving the utilization of generation from intermittent renewable energy, it enables low-carbon generation capacity,
- 2) Provides lower-cost system stabilization during peak times when energy usage is high, replacing more expensive flexibility options.
- 3) Improves utilization of existing conventional generation and postpones investments in transmission and distribution grid capacity expansion (Sanders et al., 2016).

A study in the UK estimated the cost of reinforcing the grid to connect more DERs to the system at a budget of £2.7 billion per year. However, the UK concluded that using flexibility technologies could save the electricity system £17-40 billion between now and 2050 (Sanders et al., 2016). Furthermore, the use of flexibility technologies typically increases HC and grid access by 50-100%, maximizing DERs interconnection share and minimizing operational constraint (ENA, 2021).

Taking flexibility into account will contribute to reducing renewable system investment costs. Adoption of renewable systems will primarily depend on the reduction in ESS costs. The highest levels of savings will be achieved by reducing ESS-related costs. Improving the grid by allowing more energy to be imported during periods when wholesale energy prices are cheaper would be economically beneficial.

Conclusion

The aim of this paper is to investigate the concept of flexibility, which is an important aspect in increasing the HC and management of DERs.

High penetration scenarios of DERs are known to cause difficulties for existing grids and will therefore create demand for advanced control concepts to guarantee reliable and cost-effective grid operation in the future (Von Appen et al., 2013).

This requires local, decentralized and centralized strategies, as well as more fully integrated approaches that consider technical effectiveness and economic efficiency for all stakeholders.

Flexibility can also provide "optionality", whereby additional investments in flexibility can defer decision-making on larger investments until better information is available, thereby reducing the need to make potentially regrettable decisions.

While much research and projects on flexibility have been mentioned in this paper, it is still under-represented in actual practice. There are many issues related to flexibility that need to be researched. These include;

- Integration costs of DERs into the grid,
- How to manage all flexible assets simultaneously (Freire-Barceló et al., 2022),
- Determination of flexibility parameters to be included in the distribution system,
- To facilitate flexibility management and deployment at the distribution level, standardized definitions of the distribution assets required for flexibility need to be established,
- Transmission side impact,
- Further research should also include the development of a framework that incorporates the protection of the information barrier, i.e., taking into account both the different interests of participants and the system-wide perspective for transmission and distribution systems,
- The energy market, i.e., the development and definition of new marketplaces for participation in the intraday market (Pearson et al., 2022).

Future research exploring these important issues will enable full utilization of flexibility in EDS.

Finally, we can conclude that the definition of flexibility is subjective according to the party to be implemented and the context of the project (Hussain et al., 2023). However, whether flexibility is on the DERs side or on

the consumer side, it can contribute to the stability and reliability of the system and reduce costs, postponing the need for investment.

References

- Alizadeh, M. I., Parsa Moghaddam, M., Amjady, N., Siano, P., & Sheikh-El-Eslami, M. K. (2016). Flexibility in future power systems with high renewable penetration: A review. In *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* (Vol. 57, pp. 1186–1193). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.12.200>
- Alvarez, E. F., Olmos, L., Ramos, A., Antoniadou-Plytaria, K., Steen, D., & Tuan, L. A. (2022). Values and impacts of incorporating local flexibility services in transmission expansion planning. *Electric Power Systems Research*, 212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2022.108480>
- Arbolea, P., Kippke, M. A., & Kerschler, S. (2022). Flexibility management in the low-voltage distribution grid as a tool in the process of decarbonization through electrification. *Energy Reports*, 8, 248–256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2022.01.076>
- Calero, I., Cañizares, C. A., Bhattacharya, K., & Baldick, R. (2022). Duck-Curve Mitigation in Power Grids with High Penetration of PV Generation. *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, 13(1), 314–329. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSG.2021.3122398>
- Couraud, B., Andoni, M., Robu, V., Norbu, S., Chen, S., & Flynn, D. (2023). Responsive Flexibility: A smart local energy system. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113343>
- Department of Energy, U. (2015). Chapter 3: Enabling Modernization of the Electric Power System Technology Assessments Cyber and Physical Security Designs, Architectures, and Concepts Electric Energy Storage Flexible and Distributed Energy Resources Measurements, Communications, and Controls Transmission and Distribution Components Flexible and Distributed Energy Resources.
- ENA. (2021). Flexibility Connections: Explainer and Q&A.
- Essayeh, C., & Morstyn, T. (2023). Optimal sizing for microgrids integrating distributed flexibility with the Perth West smart city as a case study. *Applied Energy*, 336. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.120846>
- European Commission. (2019). United in delivering the Energy Union and Climate Action - Setting the foundations for a successful clean energy transition.
- Freire-Barceló, T., Martín-Martínez, F., & Sánchez-Miralles, Á. (2022). A literature review of Explicit Demand Flexibility providing energy services. In *Electric Power Systems Research* (Vol. 209). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2022.107953>
- Gantenbein, D., Binding, C., Jansen, B., & Mishra, A. (2012). 2012 Sustainable Internet and ICT for Sustainability : SustainIT : Pisa, Italy, October 4-5, 2012.
- Georgiopoulos, S., Ahmadi, A. R., Do, S., Mokkalas, S., & Partner, B. (2020). UK Power Networks develop the world's first market-based approach to delivering efficient network constraint management. *CIREN - Open Access Proceedings Journal*, 2020(1), 773–775. <https://doi.org/10.1049/oap-cired.2021.0222>
- Gielen, D., Boshell, F., Saygin, D., Bazilian, M. D., Wagner, N., & Gorini, R. (2019). The role of renewable energy in the global energy transformation. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 24, 38–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2019.01.006>
- Hussain, S., Lai, C., & Eicker, U. (2023). Flexibility: Literature review on concepts, modeling, and provision method in smart grid. *Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks*, 35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.segan.2023.101113>
- iPower. (2009).
- Kaheh, Z., Kazemzadeh, R. B., & Sheikh-El-Eslami, M. K. (2019). Simultaneous consideration of the balancing market and day-ahead market in Stackelberg game for flexiramp procurement problem in the presence of the wind farms and a DR aggregator. *IET Generation, Transmission and Distribution*, 13(18), 4099–4113. <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-gtd.2018.6666>

- Local Electricity retail Markets for Prosumer smart grid Power services. (2020).
- Nouicer, A., Meeus, L., & Delarue, E. (2023). Demand-side flexibility in distribution grids: Voluntary versus mandatory contracting. *Energy Policy*, 173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2022.113342>
- Open utility. a glimpse into the future of Britain's energy economy, (n.d.). 2022.
- Pearson, S., Wellnitz, S., Crespo del Granado, P., & Hashemipour, N. (2022). The value of TSO-DSO coordination in re-dispatch with flexible decentralized energy sources: Insights for Germany in 2030. *Applied Energy*, 326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.119905>
- Pedro, A., Krutnik, M., Yadack, V. M., Pereira, L., & Morais, H. (2023). Opportunities and challenges for small-scale flexibility in European electricity markets. *Utilities Policy*, 80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jup.2022.101477>
- Reed, S. (2017). Power Prices Go Negative in Germany, a Positive for Energy Users.
- Ritchie H, R. M. R. P. Energy. (2022). *Energy. Our World in Data*;
- Sanders, D., Hart, A., & Brunert, J. (2016). An analysis of electricity system flexibility for Great Britain.
- Silva, R., Alves, E., Ferreira, R., Villar, J., & Gouveia, C. (2021). Characterization of TSO and DSO grid system services and TSO-DSO basic coordination mechanisms in the current decarbonization conte. *Energies*.
- Soto, E. A., Bosman, L. B., Wollega, E., & Leon-Salas, W. D. (2021). Peer-to-peer energy trading: A review of the literature. *Applied Energy*, 283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.116268>
- Toghranegar, S., Rabiee, A., & Soroudi, A. (2022). Enhancing the unbalanced distribution network's hosting capacity for DERs via optimal load re-phasing. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2022.104243>
- Von Appen, J., Braun, M., Stetz, T., Diwold, K., & Geibel, D. (2013). Time in the sun: The challenge of high PV penetration in the German electric grid. *IEEE Power and Energy Magazine*, 11(2), 55–64. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MPE.2012.2234407>